

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TOHON****FIRST NAME: HERMANN****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Academic writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6-14)
2. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24-32)
3. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 33-39)
4. Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) crib sheet (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 43-47)
5. Sample corrections to papers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 65-71)

HOW TO WRITE AT EUCLID

1) INTRODUCTION

Most of the activities involve many people. Their achievement comes from the people tasks nesting. As academic writing is concerned, if students or authors write, professors or peer-reviewers will assess this essay before its publishing. Becker confirms that when he said, 'tout travail artistique, de même que toute activité humaine fait intervenir les activités conjuguées d'un certain nombre, et souvent d'un grand nombre de personnes' (Any artistic work, just like any human activity, involves a certain number of combined activities, and often of a large number of people; my translation) (Becker 2006, 27). However, people cannot work together without guidelines that allow them to understand each other. A convention setting is essential to enable people to work together efficiently. Becker argues, 'les conventions facilitent l'activité collective et permettent des économies de temps, d'énergie et d'autres ressources' (Conventions facilitate collective activity and save time, energy, and other resources; my translation) (Becker 2006, 59). So, many rules guide international academy writing. This first course, 'ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1', revised by Professors Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021), focuses on how to write at EUCLID. This document contains seven chapters. However, I will successively concentrate my attention on these five concepts:

- academic writing
- American vs. British English
- plagiarism
- Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) crib sheet
- sample corrections to papers.

2) **ACADEMIC WRITING**

Chapter one focuses on essay writing. That specific writing is not simply based on self-imagination and self-liberty. Many rules guide it. Therefore, I cannot jump directly into academic writing. I should follow the rules, so it is essential to know and master them before dealing with academic essays. That is why Cleenewerck and Kabiru advise reading through the rules of thumb for writing a paper before writing the first paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 12). The practices involve the objectives, methodology, and academic writing format.

Concerning academy writing objectives, it aims to answer hypotheses on an evidence basis (Cleenewerck and Kabiru 2021, 7). As hypotheses are provisional answers to a question, it must highlight this question at the beginning. Academic writing objectives impose their methodology, which can step at the onset by asking a question and finding provisional answers. Moreover, I need evidence to confirm the hypotheses. That is the reason why researching the topic is essential. Likewise, I should have a specific state of mind: I must be creative or critical thinking (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9). I can draft the plan and write the essay when I have enough information from the research. The introduction and conclusion are written conversely: while ideas move from general to specific in the introduction, ideas move in opposite ways in the conclusion. However, both are written when the body is ready.

I synthesize that the main academy writing steps are topic – question – hypothesis- research- ideas organizing- writing. I think that all of them aim to achieve academic writing objectives. Their nesting led to answering the research question regarding format rules; for example, referencing, editing, and handling concerned.

3) **AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH**

Chapter three deals with American vs. British English. It highlights the similarities and differences between American and British English, so I should pay attention when writing or speaking to be consistent—these differences and similarities concern spelling and punctuation.

Some words have the exact spelling and different pronunciations. On the opposite, others have the same pronunciation and different spelling. Sometimes, words are the same but have different or additional meanings. Those nuances show that I must know words to avoid misunderstanding. So, it is good to deepen word knowledge in American and British English—this state of mind also concerns grammar.

Regarding grammar, SBE 'Large Collective Nouns' are considered singular in American English and plural in British English. British tend to pluralize adjectives. However, in some cases, adjectives remain singular. The pluralized adjectives rules account for instance and individual usage (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 27). Other differences are related to the participle adjectives, verbs, and adjectives uses.

On the one hand, different words express the same concept. On the other hand, distinctions are in euphemistic references and 'equality' vocabulary. Besides that, English varies from one region to another.

I observe some differences in punctuation. Date punctuation differs from American to British English. Likewise, British quotation punctuation is different from the American one. At the same time, Americans use quotation marks, and British use inverted commas. In addition, whereas the period and comma may be inside or outside closing quotation marks in British English, periods and commas are always inside completing quotation marks in American English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 32). I can mark this difference in the business salutation: Americans end with colons, where British end by a comma.

4) PLAGIARISM

Chapter four highlights plagiarism by showing what plagiarism is. I understand from Cleenewerck and Gulma's course that 'plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information' (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). If it is not harmful to borrow quotes, paraphrases, data, and visuals from another, it will be compulsory to give him credit. Otherwise, I infringe on the ethical regulation which guides academic writing. I should give credit to my quote, paraphrase, data, and visuals, so I should indicate any source of my data and visuals. Only author citation prevents plagiarism.

Cleenewerck and Gulma said, 'To avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using' (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). It is vital to cite the author and the source appropriately. I must respect the rules to cite my citation correctly, so I should care for in-text citations and the list of works cited.

About in-text citations, I make a difference between short and long quotations. When the quotation is less than four lines, I mention the quotation marks for the quote. However, there is no quotation mark for more than four lines. In this case, a new paragraph is necessary. I do not need to cite common knowledge.

5) CMS CRIB SHEET

Chapter six focuses on the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). This manual has a specific way of documenting. I can distinguish Chicago style and usage, Chicago page formatting, and Chicago end/footnotes.

Concerning abbreviations and acronyms, I can make some observations. On the one hand, I cannot use abbreviations at the beginning of the sentence, whereas scholarly abbreviations are in parentheses in the text. On the other hand, acronyms must be introduced and bracketed on first use. Furthermore, I must spell out geographic terms.

I differentiate between full caps, heading caps, and sentence caps for capitalization. I should capitalize the first character after a colon in the heading and sentence caps. The heading caps are for books, journal names, articles, and documents.

About compounds, it is sometimes good to refer to a dictionary. However, some cases, such as adjectival compounds, fractions, made-up compounds, and serial compounds, require hyphen use.

I can mainly spell out numbers in three cases: From one to hundred, at the beginning of the sentence, and the round numbers.

6) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

Chapter eight highlights sample corrections to papers. I should always watch out for punctuation. This observation concerns mainly the punctuation before and after prepositions. I must remember the comma before the preposition 'and.' I should constantly remind of commas following prepositions such as therefore, also, however, and so. I should have the same state of mind after using 'for example.' I should also consider citation punctuation and place punctuation before inverted commas. There is no space after the opening bracket.

Apart from punctuation, I should also pay attention to grammar, spelling, and abbreviations. The abbreviation of doctor is DR. I notice that it is better to use the preposition to and because respectively instead of to and due to the fact. I can observe using 'must' instead of 'have to'. The use of contraction is forbidden. I should also use "always" for things I should compulsorily do.

7) CONCLUSION

After reading the course, I have a clear mind about how to write at EUCLID. The document is understandable. The examples given helped to understand academic writing clearly. I also learn a methodology to deal with academic research. It is pretentious to say that I have mastered all rules. However, I am sure that practice makes perfect. So, this course is a handbook I will refer to during all the training and academy life.

REFERENCES

Becker, Howard. 2006. *Les Mondes de l'art [The Worlds of Art]*. Paris: Flammarion.

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